

SHORT NOTES

PISUM SATIVUM (LINN).

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Sanyal (*Calcutta Med. J.*, 1952, 49, 343) reported the sterility effect of the oil of *Pisum sativum* Linn and isolated *m*-xylohydroquinone from the said oil. The author claims that the aforementioned compound is responsible for the sterility effect. In view of this important observation, an investigation on the non-saponifiable constituents of the oil is reported herein.

The oil was saponified with methanolic potassium hydroxide and the neutral material was chromatographed on alumina to furnish an oily and a waxy hydrocarbons of unknown constitution together with β -amyrin and β -sitosterol.

* *β -Amyrin and β -Sitosterol.*—Powdered seeds of *Pisum sativum* (4174 g.) were extracted with hot petroleum ether (b. p. 60°-80°) until the extract was colorless. After removal of the solvent the red oily residue (64 g.) was heated to reflux for 8 hours with potassium hydroxide (40 g.) in water (40 c.c.), methanol (300 c.c.) and benzene (300 c.c.). The mixture was diluted with water (1000 c.c.) and then extracted with ether in a continuous extraction apparatus. The ethereal solution after washing with water was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue (23 g.), obtained after evaporation of the ether, was chromatographed on alumina (420 g.). The oily material (1.9 g.), eluted with petroleum ether (b. p. 60°-80°), was evaporatively distilled to yield (i) an oil, b.p. 80°/0.15 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4890 (Found: C, 87.10; H, 12.68%); (ii) a semi-solid material, b.p. 140-50°/0.1 mm (Found: C, 86.56; H, 13.76%). The material (600 mg.) eluted with benzene-petroleum ether (1:9 and 1:4) was rechromatographed on alumina to furnish a crystalline substance, m. p. 190-92° (80 mg.) which was crystallised six times from methanol to yield β -amyrin, m. p. 200-201°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +96 \pm 2^\circ$. (Found: C, 84.62; H, 11.81. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.43; H, 11.80%). Ames, Hålsall and Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 450) record m. p. 197-99°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +91^\circ$.

The *acetate* of β -amyrin was prepared with acetic anhydride and pyridine at room temperature and then chromatographed to afford a pure material, m. p. 234-35° after crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and alcohol. (Found: C, 82.20; H, 11.08. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.98; H, 11.19%).

The solid material together with the oil (3 g.) eluted with benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) was rechromatographed to afford, after crystallisation from alcohol, β -sitosterol, m. p. 136-37°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -34 \pm 1^\circ$. (Found: C, 84.02; H, 12.02. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{48}O$: C, 83.98; H, 10.49%). The mixed m. p. with an authentic sample (Chatterjee and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 485) remained undepressed.

The authors' thanks are due to Mrs. C. Dutta for microanalysis.

The m. p.'s are uncorrected.

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Received December 20, 1956.